

Factors Influencing Financial Performance: A Comparative Study of Public Sector Non-Life Insurers in India

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Abstract:-

A well-established and efficiently functioning insurance sector is crucial for fostering an inclusive economy and driving a country's growth. In India, the insurance industry has experienced steady expansion over the years. As an essential financial service, insurance provides financial security to both individuals and businesses.

The efficiency of insurance companies is typically assessed using various techniques, including financial performance analysis, technical efficiency, purely technical efficiency, and scale efficiency. This study examines the financial performance of public sector non-life insurance companies in India and identifies key factors influencing their performance. The determining factors considered include commissions, claims incurred, investment income, net premium earned, management soundness, and operating expenses. Financial data from 2009-10 to 2021-22 were analysed, with normality and stationarity tests conducted using E-Views statistical software. The findings indicate that New India Insurance Company Limited exhibits the strongest financial performance, followed by United India Insurance Company Limited. Among the key determinants of net profit after tax for public sector non-life insurers, claims incurred and net premium earned play a significant role.

Keywords: *Financial Performance, Net Profit after Tax, Non-life Insurance, Return on Equity.*

JEL Classifications: *G22, L25, N20*

1. Introduction:-

Generally, insurance serves as a crucial risk management tool, offering various products and services to individuals and businesses to ensure financial security (Krishnamurthy et al., 2005). Basically, the Indian insurance industry is divided into two main categories: the life insurance sector and the non-life insurance sector (Mandal & Ghosh Dastidar, 2014). since India's economy opened to private players in 1992, it was only in 2000, with the enactment of the *Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority Act*, that private insurers were officially allowed to operate in the Indian market (Ashraf & Faiz, 2018). Since then, industry has grown consistently, playing a vital role in economic development (Chakraborty & Harper, 2017; Sinha, 2007). Since the presence of private players in both life and non-life insurance segments has increased significantly (Chakraborty, 2017). In Despite of this, public sector insurance companies continue to dominate the Indian insurance market, even with the entry of private firms through foreign collaborations and investments (Ray et al., 2020).

During the COVID-19 pandemic led to an economic slowdown and inflationary pressures worldwide (IRDAI, 2022). This decline in economic growth resulted in lower demand for insurance but an increase in claims (IRDAI, 2022). Since 2021, global real insurance premiums grew by 3.4%, with the life insurance sector expanding by 4.5% and the non-life sector by 2.6%. Basically, India's insurance market, however, outpaced the global average, with the life insurance sector growing at 8.5% and the non-life sector at 5.8% (IRDAI, 2022). Since this growth is attributed to rising awareness of insurance products, supportive government policies, financial inclusion initiatives, and increasing financial literacy. In 2022, India's insurance penetration (premium as a percentage of GDP) stood at 4.2%, while insurance density (premium per capita) was \$91 (IRDAI, 2022).

The evolving landscape of the insurance industry presents both challenges and opportunities, Regulators, customers, and investors seek efficient insurers, as inefficient companies struggle to provide adequate financial security and high-quality insurance products (Ilyas & Rajasekaran, 2019). Evaluating and analyzing insurer

efficiency is essential, as it reflects their ability to adapt to industry challenges (Amanti & Siregar, 2019). Efficiency, in this context, refers to the optimal use of available resources to produce maximum output, compared to the most efficient firms in the industry (Bhatia & Mahendru, 2021). It is a key indicator of an insurer's performance, commonly measured through technical efficiency (Sinha, 2007).

Financial performance (FP) assesses a company's earnings, profitability, and overall value (Mwangi & Murigu, 2015). In the insurance industry, profitability is determined by factors such as premiums earned, returns on investment, and return on equity (Mwangi & Murigu, 2015). Additionally, insurance companies play a significant role in financing long-term projects, contributing to economic development (Morara & Sibindi, 2021). A sustainable insurance market is essential for overall economic stability, and its sustainability is closely tied to the financial performance of insurers (Morara & Sibindi, 2021). Profitability is typically measured using variables such as net profit after tax (NPAT), return on equity (ROE), and return on net earnings (RONE).

Basically, this study aims to identify the factors influencing the financial performance of public-sector general insurers in India, both at an industry-wide level and at the company level. Additionally, it provides a comparative analysis of the financial performance of public sector general insurance companies in the country.

2. Review of the Existing Research Works: -

A well-functioning insurance system plays a crucial role in a country's economic development by safeguarding businesses against financial risks (**Chakraborty & Harper, 2017**). The general insurance sector accounts for approximately 30% of total industry premiums (**Ray et al., 2020**). Several studies have examined the efficiency of insurers (**Bawa & Ruchita, 2011; Nikita Kumari, 2018; Ofori-Boateng et al., 2022; Siddiqui, 2020; Sinha, 2007**), focusing on different types of efficiency, such as technical, purely technical, and scale efficiencies (**Bhatia & Mahendru, 2021**). Additionally, environmental variables have been found to influence the efficiency scores of life insurers (**Shieh et al., 2020**).

Prominent methods for measuring efficiency include *Data Envelopment Analysis* (DEA) and *Stochastic Frontier* analysis (**Bawa & Ruchita, 2011**). DEA is

categorized into two concepts: the traditional approach, which does not account for multiple inputs, and the modern approach, which incorporates multiple inputs (**Bawa & Ruchita, 2011**). To improve efficiency, general insurance companies should invest in workforce development and technology adoption (**Ofori-Boateng et al., 2022**). However, technical efficiency does not consider cost and revenue analysis, leading researchers to focus on revenue efficiency instead (**Bhatia & Mahendru, 2021; Morara & Sibindi, 2021; Muthulakshmi, 2018**). Revenue efficiency measures an insurer's ability to deliver services effectively using available resources (**Bhatia & Mahendru, 2021**). Insurers' productivity efficiency is assessed using *constant returns to scale* and *variable returns to scale* methods (**Mandal & Ghosh Dastidar, 2014**), which fluctuate based on economic conditions.

Studies on insurers' financial performance reveal that companies with high leverage and low liquidity tend to perform better (**Nikita Kumari, 2018**). The profitability of general insurance companies is influenced by both internal and external factors. Internal factors include company-specific characteristics, while external factors encompass industry dynamics and macroeconomic variables (**Mwangi & Murigu, 2015**). Determinants of insurers' economic performance include company size and age, equity capital, underwriting risk, retention ratio, and ownership structure (**Mwangi & Murigu, 2015**). Financial performance (FP) is a subjective measure of an organization's ability to maximize revenues and profits using its assets (**Morara & Sibindi, 2021**). Commissions significantly impact FP and are critical in determining an insurer's market share (**Mulchandani et al., 2017**). Additionally, a direct relationship exists between equity capital and financial performance (**Kaur Bawa & Chattha, 2013**). Public insurance companies must focus on capital adequacy and reinsurance to ensure financial stability (**Vijay, 2019**).

Existing research emphasizes the need to evaluate insurers' performance, as it reflects the efficient utilization of resources. Performance is measured through various analyses, including financial, technical, purely technical, and scale efficiency assessments. While numerous studies examine the performance of life and non-life insurers in India, limited research has been conducted on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers. Therefore, this study aims to provide a comparative analysis of the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers in India.

3. Research Objectives: -

The objectives of the study are as follows: -

1. To assess and analyze the differences in the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers in India at an overall level.
2. To identify and evaluate the key factors influencing the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers in India.
3. To measure and examine the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers in India, along with its key determinants, at the company level.
4. To conduct a comparative analysis of the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers in India.

Based on the study objectives, the following hypotheses have been formulated:-

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers.

H₀₂: Commission does not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the overall level.

H₀₃: Net premium earned does not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the overall level.

H₀₄: Investment income does not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the overall level.

H₀₅: Claims incurred do not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the overall level.

H₀₆: Operating expenses do not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the overall level.

H₀₇: Management soundness does not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the overall level.

H₀₈: Commission does not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the company level.

H₀₉: Net premium earned does not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the company level.

H₁₀: Investment income does not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the company level.

H₁₁: Claims incurred do not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the company level.

H₁₂: Operating expenses do not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the company level.

H₁₃: Management soundness does not have a significant impact on the financial performance of public-sector non-life insurers at the company level.

5. Research Methodology: -

Basically, this descriptive study relies on secondary data to analyze the financial performance (FP) of public-sector non-life insurers in India. The study includes all four public-sector non-life insurance companies: National Insurance Company Limited (NICL), New India Insurance Company Limited (NIICL), The Oriental Insurance Company Limited (TOICL), and United India Insurance Company Limited (UIICL). The analysis covers the financial years from 2009-10 to 2021-22 using secondary data sourced from the annual reports of the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI).

To assess and analyze FP, the study considers key financial variables such as commission, net premium earned, investment income, claims incurred, operating expenses, and management soundness as determinants of financial performance. The performance itself is measured using Net Profit After Tax (NPAT), Return on Net Worth (RONW), and Return on Equity (ROE). The methodology for computing these variables is detailed in Table 1.

Based on the measurement framework in Table 1, the study computes the financial variables for each public-sector non-life insurance company for each financial year from 2009-10 to 2021-22. To identify the determinants of financial performance, the study employs Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis. Additionally, differences in FP among public-sector non-life insurers are examined using mean-variance analysis.

The regression equation used in the study is as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{COM} + \beta_2 \text{NPE} + \beta_3 \text{II} + \beta_4 \text{OE} + \beta_5 \text{MS} + \varepsilon$$

Where Y = NPAT or ROE or RONW

Where:

- Y = NPAT, ROE, or RONW
- COM = Commission
- NPE = Net Premium Earned
- II = Investment Income
- OE = Operating Expenses
- MS = Management Soundness
- α = Intercept
- ε = Error Term

Table 1 showing the Variables and their measurement: -

Particulars	Measurement or Computation
Commission (COM)	Commission paid to the agents during a year
Net Premium Earned (NPE)	Insurance premiums underwritten – Reinsurance ceded + Reinsurance accepted
Investment Income (II)	Income raised from investments in sources other than insurance
Claims Incurred (CI)	Direct claims + Reinsurance claim paid – Reinsurance claim received
Operating Expenses (OE)	Office and administration expenses, selling, and distribution expenses related to insurance products
Management Soundness (MS)	Operating expenses incurred divided by gross premium earned
Net Profit After Tax (NPAT)	Operating profit after tax
Return on Equity (ROE)	Net profit after tax divided by shareholders' equity
Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Net worth divided by shareholders' equity

(Source: Compiled by the authors)

6. Results of Data Analysis: -

The financial performance of Indian public sector non-life insurers was first analyzed at the overall level. Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of key financial variables, including commission, net premium earned, investment income, claims incurred, operating expenses, management soundness, NPAT, ROE, and RONW.

The results indicate that operating expenses, management soundness, NPAT, ROE, and RONW exhibit negative skewness, while commission, net premium earned,

investment income, and claims incurred show positive skewness. Kurtosis values suggest that commission, net premium earned, investment income, claims incurred, operating expenses, management soundness, and Return on Equity exhibit negative kurtosis, whereas NPAT and RONW exhibit positive kurtosis.

The Jarque-Bera p-values for all variables—including commission, net premium earned, investment income, claims incurred, operating expenses, management soundness, NPAT, ROE, and RONW—are greater than 0.05, confirming that these variables follow a normal distribution.

Additionally, differences in NPAT, ROE, and RONW across public sector non-life insurance companies were assessed using a test of means for equality. The results of this analysis are summarized in Table 3.

Table 2: showing the Descriptive Statistics of Key Financial Variables

Particulars	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Jarque-Bera	P-Value
Commission (COM)	753.227	332.48	1.395	-1.160	0.945	0.623
Net Premium Earned (NPE)	10137.935	4013.63	5.023	-1.274	0.799	0.670
Investment Income (II)	678.746	120.72	7.270	-1.577	1.168	0.557
Claims Incurred (CI)	9323.907	3920.98	8.050	-1.742	1.217	0.544
Operating Expenses (OE)	2614.858	864.10	-0.008	-1.230	0.763	0.682
Management Soundness (MS)	22.262	72.964	-0.329	-0.445	0.438	0.802
Net Profit After Tax (NPAT)	110.188	675.491	-1.302	1.167	2.604	0.271
Return on Equity (ROE)	0.311	4.359	-0.849	-0.295	1.300	0.521
Return on Net Worth (RONW)	-49.278	100.840	-1.787	2.212	5.269	0.071

(Source: Computed based on secondary data)

Table 3: showing the ANOVA Analysis for Financial Performance

Variable	F-Value	P-Value
Net Profit After Tax	21.511	0.014
Return on Equity	18.203	0.018
Return on Net Worth	705.101	0.001

(Source: Computed based on secondary data)

Table 4: OLS Regression – Overall Level

Variable	NPAT P-Value	ROE P-Value	RONW P-Value
Commission (COM)	0.0864	0.8685	0.2992
Claims Incurred (CI)	0.0071	0.0016	0.0204
Investment Income (II)	0.0191	0.0406	0.1525
Management Soundness (MS)	0.4593	0.2852	0.3501
Net Premium Earned (NPE)	0.0268	0.0429	0.2715
Operating Expenses (OE)	0.7654	0.5920	0.4612
Constant	0.6767	0.3256	0.4462
R ²	0.9200	0.9470	0.8730

(Source: Computed based on secondary data)

Analysis of ANOVA and OLS Regression Results

The ANOVA results indicate significant differences in NPAT, ROE, and RONW among public sector non-life insurers. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that financial performance, as measured by NPAT, ROE, and RONW, varies across insurers at the overall level.

To identify the key determinants of financial performance, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis was conducted (Table 4). The results highlight that:-

- **Net Profit After Tax (NPAT):** Significantly influenced by claims incurred, investment income, and net premium earned, explaining 92.0% of the variation. However, commission, management soundness, and operating expenses do not have a significant impact.

- **Return on Equity (ROE):** Claims incurred, investment income, and net premium earned significantly affect ROE, accounting for 94.7% of the variation. Conversely, commission, management soundness, and operating expenses do not contribute significantly.
- **Return on Net Worth (RONW):** Primarily driven by claims incurred, which explains 87.3% of the variation. Other variables, including commission, investment income, management soundness, net premium earned, and operating expenses, do not have a significant effect.

These findings suggest that NPAT and ROE across public sector non-life insurers are predominantly influenced by claims incurred, investment income, and net premium earned. However, the key determinant of RONW is claims incurred.

Financial Performance and Determinants of NICL

Table 5: OLS Regression – NICL

Variable	NPAT (P-value)	ROE (P-value)	RONW (P-value)
Commission	0.0732	0.0374	0.3416
Claims incurred	0.0128	0.0006	0.0404
Investment Income	0.0052	0.0033	0.0500
Management Soundness	0.4341	0.0211	0.4696
Net Premium Earned	0.0006	0.0006	0.9018
Operating Expenses	0.3959	0.0287	0.1356
Constant	0.2824	0.0109	0.5320
R ²	0.972	0.977	0.734

(Source: Computed based on secondary data)

Since Table 5 shall try to present the financial performance and key determinants of NPAT, ROE, and RONW for National Insurance Company Limited (NICL):

- **NPAT:** Significantly influenced by claims incurred, investment income, and net premium earned, with an explanatory power of 97.2%. Commission, management soundness, and operating expenses do not have a notable impact.

- **ROE:** Affected by multiple factors, including commission, claims incurred, investment income, management soundness, net premium earned, and operating expenses, explaining 97.7% of the variation.
- **RONW:** Primarily determined by claims incurred and investment income, accounting for 73.4% of the variation. Other variables exhibit an insignificant impact.

Overall, these results emphasize the pivotal role of claims incurred and investment income in shaping the financial performance of NIICL, while other factors have varying degrees of influence.

Following are the various Determinants of NPAT, ROE, and RONW of New India Insurance Company Limited (NIICL) are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: showing the OLS Regression – NIICL

Variable	NPAT (P-value)	ROE (P-value)	RONW (P-value)
Commission	0.0732	0.0374	0.3416
Claims Incurred	0.0128	0.0006	0.0404
Investment Income	0.0052	0.0033	0.0500
Management Soundness	0.4341	0.0211	0.4696
Net Premium Earned	0.0006	0.0006	0.9018
Operating Expenses	0.3959	0.0287	0.1356
Constant	0.2824	0.0109	0.5320
R ²	0.972	0.977	0.734

(Source: Computed based on secondary data)

Since the net profit after tax (NPAT) of NIICL is been significantly influenced by various factors such as commission, claims incurred, management soundness, and net premium earned, accounting for 96.9% of the variation. However, investment income and operating expenses do not have a significant impact on NPAT. The Return on Equity (ROE) of NIICL is primarily affected by claims incurred, with a significant influence of 84%, while all other variables remain insignificant. The Return on Net Worth (RONW) of NIICL is significantly impacted by net premium earned, explaining 74.2% of the variation, whereas all other variables do not show a significant effect.

Following are the various determinants of NPAT, ROE, and RONW for The Orient Insurance Company Limited (TOICL) are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: showing the OLS Regression – TOICL

Variable	NPAT (P-value)	ROE (P-value)	RONW (P-value)
Commission	0.8571	0.6553	0.4224
Claims incurred	0.0015	0.0001	0.0374
Investment Income	0.0724	0.3483	0.0301
Management Soundness	0.6344	0.0213	0.6789
Net Premium Earned	0.0022	0.0008	0.4657
Operating Expenses	0.0085	0.0038	0.7809
Constant	0.7333	0.0274	0.9561
R ²	0.971	0.985	0.934

(Source: Computed based on secondary data)

Since the net profit after tax (NPAT) of TOICL is significantly influenced by claims incurred, net premium earned, and operating expenses, accounting for 97.1% of the variation. However, commission, investment income, and management soundness do not have a significant impact on NPAT. The Return on Equity (ROE) of TOICL is primarily affected by claims incurred, management soundness, net premium earned, and operating expenses, with a significance level of 98.5%, while all other variables remain insignificant. The Return on Net Worth (RONW) is significantly impacted by commission and investment income, explaining 93.4% of the variation, whereas the remaining variables do not exhibit a notable effect.

Following are the determinants of NPAT, ROE, and RONW for United India Insurance Company Limited (UIICL) are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: showing the OLS Regression – UIICL

Variable	NPAT P-value	ROE P-value	RONW P-value
Commission	0.4076	0.5360	0.5138
Claims incurred	0.0029	0.0043	0.0500
Investment Income	0.9103	0.7480	0.0756
Management Soundness	0.9262	0.0405	0.8334
Net Premium Earned	0.0087	0.0095	0.5092
Operating Expenses	0.8067	0.0241	0.5277

Variable	NPAT P-value	ROE P-value	RONW P-value
Constant	0.9886	0.0362	0.3107
R ²	0.5800	0.9330	0.9040

(Source: Computed based on secondary data)

Since the Net Profit After Tax (NPAT) of UIICL is significantly influenced by claims incurred and net premium earned, accounting for 58% of the variation. However, commission, investment income, management soundness, and operating expenses do not have a significant impact on NPAT. The Return on Equity (ROE) of UIICL is significantly affected by claims incurred, management soundness, net premium earned, and operating expenses, contributing to 93.3% of the variation, while all other variables remain insignificant. Similarly, the Return on Net Worth (RONW) is primarily impacted by claims incurred, explaining 90.4% of the variation, with all other factors showing no significant effect.

7. Discussions:-

Basically this study aims to analyze and compare the financial performance (FP) of public sector non-life insurers in India. The FP of these companies is assessed using Net Profit After Tax (NPAT), Return on Equity (ROE), and Return on Net Worth (RONW).

Since the mean NPAT scores indicate that NIICL (930.50) and UIICL (150.69) outperform NICTL (-435.60) and TOICL (-204.84). Similarly, in terms of ROE, NIICL (3.51) and UIICL (0.316) show better returns compared to NICTL (-1.95) and TOICL (-0.63). Regarding RONW, NIICL has a positive score (8.05), while NICTL (-102.62), TOICL (-13.53), and UIICL (-150.69) have negative mean scores. Overall, NIICL demonstrates the strongest financial performance, followed by UIICL, whereas NICTL and TOICL show moderate performance in comparison. These findings highlight significant differences in the financial performance of non-life insurers in India.

This study shall align with the findings of Sinha and Bandopadhyay (2015), who concluded that financial performance varies significantly among public and private general insurers, as well as among individual public insurers. The key determinants of NPAT and ROE for public sector non-life insurers are claims incurred, investment

income, and net premium earned, while RONW is primarily influenced by claims incurred. However, the analysis of individual public insurers reveals that these determinants vary across companies.

Basic common factors influencing NPAT among public insurers include claims incurred and net premium earned. Similarly, ROE is predominantly affected by claims incurred, net premium earned, management soundness, and operating expenses. In contrast, RONW is influenced by multiple factors, varying across different insurers. This study differs from Morara and Sibindi (2021), who identified investment income as a major determinant of financial performance in Kenyan insurance companies.

Generally, the critical factors contributing to the financial performance of the selected insurers include claims incurred, investment income, net premiums earned, management soundness, and operating expenses.

8. Conclusions:-

Generally Insurance is a crucial financial service that provides policyholders with financial security. In India, the insurance sector was privatized in 2000, leading to the entry of several private insurers in both the life and non-life segments. Currently, the Indian insurance industry is in a growth phase.

The study shall aim to analyze and compare the financial performance (FP) of public sector non-life insurers in India. The findings reveal significant differences in the FP of these insurers, with NIICL emerging as the best performer, followed by UIICL. Additionally, the study highlights that the factors influencing financial performance vary across insurers.

Basically the common determinants of NPAT among public sector non-life insurers are claims incurred and net premium earned. Similarly, ROE is predominantly influenced by claims incurred, net premium earned, management soundness, and operating expenses.

This research study shall try to cover data up to March 31, 2022, and does not consider subsequent periods, which is a key limitation. Future research could focus on evaluating the financial performance of private sector non-life insurers and comparing

it with that of public sector insurers, particularly in the pre- and post-pandemic periods.

References:-

- ✧ Morara, P., & Sibindi, A. (2021). Determinants of financial performance of insurance companies in Kenya. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(2), 1-17.
- ✧ Sinha, A., & Bandopadhyay, A. (2015). Financial performance of private and public general insurers in India: A comparative study. *Indian Journal of Finance*, 9(5), 32-45.
- ✧ Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI). (2022). *Annual report 2021-22*. Retrieved from <https://www.irdai.gov.in>
- ✧ Government of India. (2000). *The Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority Act, 1999*. Ministry of Finance, New Delhi.
- ✧ National Insurance Company Limited (NICL). (2022). *Financial statements and performance reports 2021-22*. Retrieved from <https://www.nationalinsurance.nic.co.in>
- ✧ United India Insurance Company Limited (UIICL). (2022). *Annual financial report 2021-22*. Retrieved from <https://uiic.co.in>
- ✧ The Oriental Insurance Company Limited (TOICL). (2022). *Financial performance summary 2021-22*. Retrieved from <https://orientalinsurance.org.in>
- ✧ New India Assurance Company Limited (NIICL). (2022). *Annual performance report 2021-22*. Retrieved from <https://newindia.co.in>
- ✧ Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI). (2022). *Annual report 2021-22*. Retrieved from <https://www.irdai.gov.in>
- ✧ Government of India. (2000). *The Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority Act, 1999*. Ministry of Finance, New Delhi.
- ✧ National Insurance Company Limited (NICL). (2022). *Financial statements and performance reports 2021-22*. Retrieved from <https://www.nationalinsurance.nic.co.in>
- ✧ United India Insurance Company Limited (UIICL). (2022). *Annual financial report 2021-22*. Retrieved from <https://uiic.co.in>
- ✧ The Oriental Insurance Company Limited (TOICL). (2022). *Financial performance summary 2021-22*. Retrieved from <https://orientalinsurance.org.in>
- ✧ New India Assurance Company Limited (NIICL). (2022). *Annual performance report 2021-22*. Retrieved from <https://newindia.co.in>